

IMPROVED RATIO-CUM-PRODUCT TYPE EXPONENTIAL ESTIMATORS OF POPULATION MEAN UNDER TWO PHASE SAMPLING FOR STRATIFICATION

Subhash Kumar Yadav, Sant Sharan Mishra, Lakhan Singh^{1*}, Alok Kumar Shukla² and Dushyant Tyagi³

Department of Mathematics and Statistics (A Centre of Excellence), Dr. R.M.L. Avadh University, Faizabad - 224 001, India.

¹Department of Statistics, H.N.B.G. Central University, Srinagar - 264 174, India.

²Department of Statistics, D. A. V. College, Kanpur - 208 001, India.

³Department of Economics, Zakir Husain P.G. Evening College, New Delhi - 110 002, India.

E-mail : drsinghlakahan@gmail.com

Abstract : In this paper the estimation of population mean using ratio-cum-product exponential type estimators under two phase (double) sampling scheme for stratification has been taken into account. The expressions for the bias and mean square error of proposed estimator have been obtained up to the first order of approximation. The value of the characterizing scalar which minimizes the mean square error (MSE) of the proposed estimator has been obtained and the minimum value of MSE of proposed estimator is also obtained. A comparison has also been made of proposed estimator with the existing estimators of population mean in double sampling for stratification. To meet out the theoretical findings, an empirical study is also carried out.

Key words : Auxiliary variable, Double sampling, Stratification, Bias, Mean square error.

1. Introduction

It is well established that the excellent use of auxiliary information enhances the efficiencies of the estimators of the corresponding parameters. The variable, which provides the auxiliary information is known as the auxiliary variable and is highly positively or negatively correlated with the main variable Y under study. It is generally denoted by X . When X is positively correlated with Y , ratio type estimators are used for the estimation of population parameters, while product type estimators are used when Y and X are negatively correlated with each other.

Cochran (1940) utilized the positively correlated auxiliary information and proposed the traditional ratio estimator of population mean of study variable. Robson (1957) utilized the negatively correlated auxiliary information and proposed the traditional product estimator of population mean. Many authors utilized positively and negatively correlated auxiliary information for improved estimation of population mean. The latest references can be made of Yan and Tian (2010), Yadav

(2011), Solanki *et al.* (2012), Jeelani *et al.* (2013), Yadav and Kadilar (2013).

2. Materials and Methods

Let us consider a heterogeneous population consisting of N distinct and identifiable units for the main characteristic (variable) Y under study. Let this heterogeneous population is divided into L different strata of size $N_h (h = 1, 2, \dots, L)$ with $W_h = \frac{N_h}{N}$ as strata weights. Two phase sampling scheme for stratification is used when these strata weights are not known in practice. We have used the following procedure for two phase sampling scheme for stratification as given by Tailor *et al.* (2014),

- (1) A sample of size n' is drawn at first phase using simple random sampling without replacement technique and the observations are taken on auxiliary variable X only.
- (2) This sample of size n' is stratified into L strata based on auxiliary variable. Let n'_h be the

number of units in h th stratum ($h = 1, 2, \dots, L$)

such that $\sum_{h=1}^L n'_h = n'$.

- (3) From these n' units, a sample of size $n_h = v_h n'_h$ is drawn, where $0 < v_h < 1$ is the predetermined probability of selecting a sample of size n_h from strata of size n'_h and it constitutes a sample of size $\sum_{h=1}^L n_h = n$. From this sample observations on both the variables Y and X are taken.

In this manuscript following notations are used,

$n = \sum_{h=1}^L n_h$ - Size of the sample at second phase

$w_h = \frac{n_h}{n}$ - h th stratum weight for the second phase sample

$\bar{Y}_h = \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} y_{hi}$ - h th stratum mean for the study variable Y

$\bar{X}_h = \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} x_{hi}$ - h th stratum mean for the auxiliary variable X

$S_y^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{h=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (y_{hi} - \bar{Y}_h)^2$ - Population mean square deviation for the study variable Y

$S_x^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{h=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (x_{hi} - \bar{X}_h)^2$ - Population mean square deviation for the auxiliary variable

$S_{yh}^2 = \frac{1}{N_h-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (y_{hi} - \bar{Y}_h)^2$ - h th stratum mean square deviation for the study variable Y

$S_{xh}^2 = \frac{1}{N_h-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (x_{hi} - \bar{X}_h)^2$ - h th stratum mean square deviation for the auxiliary variable X

$S_{yjh} = \frac{1}{N_h-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (y_{hi} - \bar{Y}_h)(x_{hi} - \bar{X}_h)$ - Covariance

between y and x in h th stratum

$\rho_{yxh} = \frac{S_{yjh}}{S_{yh} S_{xh}}$ - Correlation coefficient between y

and x in the h th stratum

$\bar{y}_{ds} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{h=1}^L w_h \bar{y}_h$ - Unbiased estimator of population mean \bar{Y} in second phase sampling

$\bar{x}_{ds} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{h=1}^L w_h \bar{x}_h$ - Unbiased estimator of population mean in second phase sampling

$\bar{y}_h = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} y_{hi}$ - h th stratum mean at second phase sampling for the study variable Y

$\bar{x}_h = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} x_{hi}$ - h th stratum mean at second phase sampling for the auxiliary variable X

$\bar{x}'_h = \frac{1}{n'_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n'_h} x_{hi}$ - h th stratum mean at first phase sampling for the auxiliary variable X

$f = \frac{n'}{N}$ - First phase sampling fraction

Ige and Tripathi (1987) proposed the following ratio type estimator in double sampling scheme for stratification as

$$\hat{Y}_{CRD} = \bar{y}_{ds} \frac{\bar{x}'}{\bar{x}_{ds}} \quad (1)$$

The product type estimator of population mean under double sampling scheme for stratification as

$$\hat{Y}_{CPD} = \bar{y}_{ds} \frac{\bar{x}_{ds}}{\bar{x}'} \quad (2)$$

The biases and mean square errors of the estimators in Equations (1) and (2), respectively are

$$B(\hat{Y}_{CRD}) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} \left[\sum_{h=1}^L \frac{W_h}{n'} \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \left(R_x S_{yh}^2 - S_{yjh} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$B(\hat{Y}_{CPD}) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} \left[\sum_{h=1}^L \frac{W_h}{n'} \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yjh} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$MSE(\hat{Y}_{CRD}) = S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \left(S_{yh}^2 + R_x^2 S_{xh}^2 - 2R_x S_{yxh} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$MSE(\hat{Y}_{CPD}) = S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \left(S_{yh}^2 + R_x^2 S_{xh}^2 + 2R_x S_{yxh} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where, $R_x = \frac{\bar{Y}}{\bar{X}}$ and $W_h = \frac{N_h}{N}$.

Taylor *et al.* (2014) proposed the following exponential ratio and product type estimators of population mean in double sampling scheme for stratification respectively as

$$\hat{Y}_{Red}^{st} = \bar{y}_{ds} \exp \left[\frac{\bar{x}' - \bar{x}_{ds}}{\bar{x}' + \bar{x}_{ds}} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st} = \bar{y}_{ds} \exp \left[\frac{\bar{x}_{ds} - \bar{x}'}{\bar{x}_{ds} + \bar{x}'} \right] \quad (8)$$

The biases and mean square errors of estimators in Equations (7) and (8), up to the first order of approximation are respectively

$$B(\hat{Y}_{Red}^{st}) = \frac{1}{8\bar{X}} \left[3S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \left(3S_{xh}^2 - S_{yxh} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

$$B(\hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st}) = \frac{1}{8\bar{X}} \left[\frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \left(4S_{yxh} - R_x S_{xh}^2 \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$MSE(\hat{Y}_{Red}^{st}) = S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \times \left(S_{yh}^2 + \frac{R_x^2}{5} S_{xh}^2 \left(1 - \frac{\beta_{yxh}}{R_x} \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

$$MSE(\hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st}) = S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) \times \left(S_{yh}^2 + \frac{R_x^2}{4} S_{xh}^2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_{yxh}}{R_x} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

Where,

$$\beta_{yxh} = \rho_{yxh} \left(\frac{S_{yh}}{S_{xh}} \right).$$

3. Proposed Estimators

Motivated by Taylor *et al.* (2014), we proposed the following exponential ratio-cum-product type estimator under two phase sampling for stratification as

$$\tau_{RCP}^{st} = \bar{y}_{ds} \left[\alpha \exp \left(\frac{\bar{x}' - \bar{x}_{ds}}{\bar{x}' + \bar{x}_{ds}} \right) + (1-\alpha) \exp \left(\frac{\bar{x}_{ds} - \bar{x}'}{\bar{x}_{ds} + \bar{x}'} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

Where, α is a suitably chosen constant to be determined such that the mean square error of the estimator in Equation (13) is minimum.

To study the large sample properties of the proposed estimator τ_{RCP}^{st} , we define

$$\bar{y}_{ds} = \bar{Y}(1 + e_0), \bar{x}_{ds} = \bar{X}(1 + e_1) \text{ and } \bar{x}' = \bar{X}(1 + e_1')$$

such that $E(e_0) = E(e_1) = E(e_1') = 0$ and

$$E(e_0^2) = \frac{V(\bar{y}_{ds})}{\bar{Y}^2} = \frac{1}{\bar{Y}^2} \left[S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yh}^2 \right],$$

$$E(e_1^2) = \frac{V(\bar{x}_{ds})}{\bar{X}^2} = \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{xh}^2 \right],$$

$$E(e_1'^2) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right], \quad E(e_0 e_1) = \frac{Cov(\bar{y}_{ds}, \bar{x}_{ds})}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right],$$

$$E(e_0 e_1') = \frac{1}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right], \quad E(e_1 e_1') = \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right].$$

The bias and the mean square error of the estimator τ_{RCP}^{st} up to the first order of approximation respectively are

$$B(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) = \bar{Y} \left[\left(\frac{3}{8} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) E(e_1'^2) - \left(\frac{1}{8} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) E(e_1^2) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \alpha \right) \times E(e_0 e_1) - \left(\frac{1}{2} - \alpha \right) E(e_0 e_1') - \frac{1}{4} E(e_1 e_1') \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
MSE(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) &= \bar{Y}^2 \left[E(e_0^2) + \frac{1}{4} E(e_1^2) + \frac{1}{4} E(e_1'^2) \right. \\
&\quad \left. E(e_0 e_1) - E(e_0 e_1') - \frac{1}{2} E(e_0 e_1') + \alpha^2 \{ E(e_1^2) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + E(e_1'^2) - 2E(e_1 e_1') \} - \alpha \{ E(e_1^2) + E(e_1'^2) + 2E(e_0 e_1) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - 2E(e_0 e_1') - 2E(e_1 e_1') \} \right] \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

Which is minimum for

$$\begin{aligned}
&\{ E(e_1^2) + E(e_1'^2) + 2E(e_0 e_1) \\
&\quad - 2E(e_0 e_1') - 2E(e_1 e_1') \} = \frac{A}{2B}
\end{aligned}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= E(e_1^2) + E(e_1'^2) + 2E(e_0 e_1) - 2E(e_0 e_1') - 2E(e_1 e_1') \\
&= \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{xh}^2 \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] + 2 \frac{1}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right] - 2 \frac{1}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] \\
&\quad - 2 \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
B &= E(e_1^2) + E(e_1'^2) - 2E(e_1 e_1') \\
&= \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{xh}^2 \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - 2 \frac{1}{\bar{X}^2} \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The minimum mean square error of τ_{RCP}^{st} is

$$\begin{aligned}
MSE_{min}(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) &= \bar{Y}^2 \left[E(e_0^2) + \frac{E(e_1^2)}{4} + \frac{E(e_1'^2)}{4} + E(e_0 e_1) - E(e_0 e_1') \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{E(e_1 e_1')}{2} - \frac{A^2}{2B} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left[\left[S_y^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yh}^2 \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{xh}^2 \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + R_x \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - R_x \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] - \frac{1}{2} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - \bar{Y}^2 \frac{A^2}{2B} \right] \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

4. Efficiency Conditions

From Equations (5) and (16), we have

$$MSE_{min}(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) - MSE(\hat{Y}_{CRD}) < 0, \text{ If,}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left[\frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 3R_x \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - R_x \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] - \frac{1}{2} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - \bar{Y}^2 \frac{A^2}{2B} \right] < 0 \quad (17)
\end{aligned}$$

From Equations (6) and (16), we have that the proposed estimator τ_{RCP}^{st} is better than the estimator \hat{Y}_{CPD} , if $MSE_{min}(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) - MSE(\hat{Y}_{CPD}) < 0$ i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left[\frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - R_x \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - R_x \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] - \frac{1}{2} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - \bar{Y}^2 \frac{A^2}{2B} \right] < 0 \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

From Equations (11) and (16), we have

$$MSE_{min}(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) - MSE(\hat{Y}_{Red}^{st}) < 0 \text{ If,}$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] \right]$$

Table 1 : Population [Source: Gujarati (4th Edi.), p. 237].
 Y : Thousands of wildcats, X : per barrel price, Z : time

	Stratum I	Stratum II		Stratum I	Stratum II
N_h	14	14	S_{xh}^2	1.25878	0.25808
n'_h	10	10	S_{zh}^2	81.2088	55.3242
n_h	5	5	S_{yxh}	0.511	0.07806
\bar{Y}_h	8.62429	11.6636	S_{yxh}	0.33857	-3.94599
\bar{X}_h	4.47	4.40214	S_y^2	3.46138	
\bar{Z}_h	21.1429	12.3571	S_x^2	0.731536	
S_{yh}^2	0.86519	1.34992	S_z^2	85.75	

Table 2 : MSE and PRE values of different estimators.

Estimators	MSE	PRE	Estimators	MSE	PRE
\hat{Y}_{CRD}	0.198676	100	\hat{Y}_{CPD}	1.21037	100
\hat{Y}_{Red}^{st}	0.108891	182.453	\hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st}	0.36705	329.756
τ_{RCP}^{st}	0.053542	371.065	τ_{RCP}^{st}	0.053542	2260.599

$$+R_x \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{5}{4} \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right]$$

$$-R_x \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] - \frac{1}{2} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - \bar{Y}^2 \frac{A^2}{2B} < 0 \quad (19)$$

The estimator τ_{RCP}^{st} is better than the estimator \hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st} if

$$MSE_{min}(\tau_{RCP}^{st}) - MSE(\hat{Y}_{Ped}^{st}) < 0 \text{ If, i.e.,}$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[S_x^2 \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{4} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] \right]$$

$$+R_x \left[S_{yx} \left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) + \frac{3}{4} \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{h=1}^L W_h \left(\frac{1}{v_h} - 1 \right) S_{yxh} \right]$$

$$-R_x \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_{yxh} \right] - \frac{1}{2} R_x^2 \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{n'} \right) S_x^2 \right] - \bar{Y}^2 \frac{A^2}{2B} < 0 \quad (20)$$

5. Empirical Study

To justify the performances of the proposed and existing estimators of population mean in stratified random sampling, we have considered the following population whose statistics are given in Table 1. The MSE and percent relative efficiency (PRE) values for different estimators are given in Table 2.

6. Results and Conclusion

In this manuscript, we have proposed the improved ratio-cum-product type exponential estimators of population mean under two phase sampling for stratification. We have found the minimum mean squared error of proposed estimator for the optimum value of the characterizing scalar. In empirical study, we observe from Table 2 that the proposed estimator τ_{RCP}^{st} has lesser mean square errors than the other mentioned ratio and product estimators of population mean under two phase sampling for stratification. Thus, we infer that the proposed ratio cum product estimator should be

preferred for the estimation of population mean in two phase sampling for stratification.

Acknowledgement

Authors are highly thankful to the Editor-in-Chief and anonymous reviewers for their fruitful comments and suggestions to improve the quality of this paper.

References

Cochran, W. G. (1940). The estimation of the yields of the cereal experiments by sampling for the Ratio of grain to total produce. *Jour. Agri. Sci.*, **59**, 1225-1226.

Ige, A. F. and T. P. Tripathi (1987). On doubling for stratification and use of auxiliary information. *J. Ind. soc. Agricul. Statist.*, **39**, 191-201.

Jeelani, M. I., S. Maqbool and S. A. Mir (2013). Modified Ratio Estimators of Population Mean Using Linear Combination of Co-efficient of Skewness and Quartile Deviation. *International Journal of Modern Mathematical Sciences*, **6**, **3**, 174-183.

Robson, D. S. (1957). Application of multivariate polykeys to the theory of unbiased ratio type estimation. *J. Amer. Stat. Assoc.*, **52**, 411-422.

Solanki, R. S., H. P. Singh and A. Rathour (2012). An alternative estimator for estimating the finite population mean using auxiliary information in sample surveys. *International Scholarly Research Network : Probability and Statistics*, **2012**, 1-14.

- Taylor, R., S. Chouhan and J-M. Kim (2014). Ratio and Product Type Exponential Estimators of Population Mean in Double Sampling for Stratification. *Communications for Statistical Applications and Methods*, **21**, **1**, 1-9.
- Yadav, S. K. (2011). Efficient estimators for population variance using auxiliary information. *Global Journal of Mathematical Sciences : Theory and Practical*, **3**, 369-376.
- Yadav, S. K. and G. Kadilar (2013). Improved class of ratio and product estimators. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, **219**, 10726–10731.
- Yan, Z. and B. Tian (2010). Ratio method to the mean estimation using co-efficient of skewness of auxiliary variable, *ICICA* , Part II, *CCIS* **106**, pp. 103–110.